

CHANGING FEATURES OF INNOVATION MANAGEMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

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Annotatsiya: maqolada raqamlashtirish sharoitida innovatsion rivojlanishni boshqarish zamonaviy biznes uchun dolzarbligi, innovatsiyalarni samarali boshqarish korxonaning raqobatbardoshligini oshirish, balki uning uzoq muddatli rivojlanishi uchun barqaror asos yaratish imkonini berishi va innovatsiyalar yangi sanoatni yaratishga yo'naltirilishi yoki mavjud sanoatga birlashtirilishi mumkinligi to'g'risida bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: boshqaruvni raqamlashtirish, innovatsion rivojlanish, qarorlar qabul qilish, raqobatbardoshligini oshirish, boshqarish texnologiyalari, innovatsion faoliyat.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается актуальность управления инновационным развитием для современного бизнеса в условиях цифровизации, показано, что эффективное управление инновациями позволяет не только повысить конкурентоспособность предприятия, но и создать устойчивую основу для его долгосрочного развития, а инновации могут быть направлены на создание новой отрасли или интегрированы в существующую.

Ключевые слова: цифровизация управления, инновационное развитие, принятие решений, повышение конкурентоспособности, управленческие технологии, инновационная деятельность.

Abstract: The article describes the relevance of innovative development management for modern business in the context of digitalization, the fact that effective innovation management allows not only to increase the competitiveness of an enterprise, but also to create a stable basis for its long-term development, and that innovations can be directed towards the creation of a new industry or integrated into an existing one.

Keywords: In the context of digitalization Innovative development requires enterprises not only to invest in the latest technologies, but also to change their approach to management, organizational culture and human resources. The introduction of digital technologies, such as automation of production lines, the use of artificial intelligence, technology learning, digital platforms for communicating with customers and partners, requires significant changes in management practices and the ability to adapt to new conditions. Digital technologies allow for the effective collection and analysis of large amounts of data, which allows for more informed decisions, optimization of production and improvement of customer interactions through personalized offers and marketing strategies.

However, in the context of digitalization Innovation is not a smooth process. This creates new challenges for businesses, including the need to modernize infrastructure, adapt employees to new technologies, manage organizational changes, and address data security and privacy issues. In addition, with globalization and increased competition, businesses are forced

to respond more quickly to changes in the market environment, which requires high flexibility and the ability to quickly implement innovations.

Therefore, managing innovative development in the context of digitalization is relevant for modern business, as it allows not only to increase the competitiveness of the enterprise, but also to create a stable foundation for its long-term development. The integration of new technologies into management and production processes, the training of relevant personnel, and the support of an innovative culture are becoming important components for enterprises to successfully overcome the challenges of the digital age.

The study of innovative development occupies a central place in the work of many scientists who analyze its theoretical and practical aspects. Attention is paid to determining the essence of innovative development, its role in ensuring sustainable economic growth rates, the competitiveness of enterprises and countries. In particular, the mechanisms for introducing innovations, their impact on production efficiency and socio-economic development, as well as methods for assessing the effectiveness of innovative projects are being studied.

In this regard, according to H. Gumba, "innovative development is not only the main innovative process, but also the development of a system of factors and conditions necessary for its implementation, that is, the development of innovative potential"[1]. O. Adamenko argues that "innovative development is the activity of an enterprise based on a constant search for new methods and means of satisfying consumer needs and increasing business efficiency; development that involves expanding the boundaries of innovative activity and introducing innovations into all areas of the enterprise's activities "[2].

S. Ilyashenko explains in his research that "innovative development is a management process based on the constant search and use of new methods and directions for realizing the potential of enterprises in changing environmental conditions within the framework of the chosen task and the motivation adopted for the activity, and is associated with the transformation of existing ones and the formation of new sales markets" [3].

By the degree of novelty, innovations are divided into radical, simple, modifying and pseudo-innovations. Radical innovations (revolutionary, fundamental) lead to significant changes in the technological or economic environment, create new markets or industries. Simple innovations are the gradual development of existing technologies, while modifications are aimed at improving existing products or processes. Pseudo-innovations, although they may seem like innovations, in fact only imitate changes, without creating a significant additional effect. By the novelty of the place of application, innovations can be aimed at creating a new industry or integrating into an existing industry.

Innovation management in the context of digitalization is characterized by a number of specific features that arise as a result of the rapid development of technologies and changes in business processes. Digitalization creates new opportunities for improving the effectiveness of innovation management, and also creates the need to adapt traditional approaches to managing changes in the organization. The main feature of innovation management in the digital era is the integration of digital technologies into all aspects of the enterprise's activities. This includes the use of big data, analytics, artificial intelligence, blockchain technologies and other tools to optimize processes and increase the speed of decision-making.

Such technologies allow not only to predict market trends, but also to quickly adapt business models to changes in the external environment. Digital innovations provide the

necessary conditions for the development and implementation of other product innovations aimed at commercialization. “Innovative digitalization is considered from the point of view of providing the necessary infrastructure for mutual cooperation of participants in the innovation process, since digital technologies themselves are innovations for enterprises”[4].

Enterprise digital innovation is a means of leveraging digital processes, resources, and services based on digital transformation technologies. The goals of enterprise digital transformation vary from implementing individual digital solutions to creating cultural transformations and ecosystems (Table 1).

Table 1

Enterprise digitalization goals

Typical goals of digital transformation	Brief description
Improve operational efficiency	Reduce costs, increase reliability, and solve operational problems by implementing digital solutions.
Increasing the competitiveness of the company's products and services	Developing new products using digital technologies; transitioning to new business models using digital technologies to maintain the company's competitive position; improving customer service levels
Improving the quality of business solutions and business transparency	Collecting new data and converting existing data into digital format, and implementing data analysis tools: monitoring company activities; improving the quality of business decisions made and eliminating human errors.
Implementation of innovative projects based on digital technologies	Development and implementation of innovative solutions based on digital technologies; implementation of solutions for external customers.
Increasing the company's "viability" level	Digital, cultural, organizational, and often operational transformations (“digital enterprise”) to qualitatively transform the enterprise: speed and flexibility of business processes and resource utilization; rapid response to changing external conditions; customer focus.
Aligning the company's business with the ecosystem (platform)	Monetizing a company's existing customer base or technology platform by creating a digital ecosystem; the company's exit from a traditional industry.

The main specific elements of digitization for an enterprise are:

- digitalization is comprehensive in nature, implying the creation of a “digital ecosystem” and a “digital platform” for information exchange between the structural divisions of the enterprise. This allows for quick decision-making, effective process management, and processing of large volumes of data;
- digitalization ensures continuous access to information about the status of all processes, systems and structures of the enterprise, including data collection, processing and analysis;
- The use of digital technologies helps accelerate decision-making, which is crucial for ensuring the competitiveness of an enterprise.

The integration of digital technologies into the activities of the enterprise provides a number of advantages, in particular, improving the information interaction between the stages of the life cycle of products or services. Digital transformation allows you to significantly increase the efficiency of business processes by introducing innovations and adapting business models to the requirements of the modern digital economy. According to research, the speed of implementation of digital technologies in the enterprise depends on two main factors.

The first in this regard is the organization's internal capabilities and readiness for change, and the second is external incentives that contribute to digital transformation. Innovation management is a key factor in ensuring the competitiveness and sustainable development of an enterprise in the conditions of a modern economy characterized by rapid change and a high level of uncertainty[5]. Effective management of innovation processes helps to create new products, technologies, services or business models that meet the changing needs of the market and consumers.

In conclusion, the features of innovation management are determined by the complexity and multifaceted nature of innovation activities, which cover all stages - from ideation to commercialization. The main characteristics of this process are the uncertainty of results, the need for significant financial and human resources, as well as a high level of risks associated with the integration of various functional areas of the enterprise. Innovation management involves creating a favorable environment for the generation of new ideas, their evaluation, development and implementation.

References:

1. Gumba Kh. M. Theoretical foundations of innovative development of enterprises in the construction industry: monograph / Kh. M. gumba; Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation, Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Professional Education "Moscow. state is building. un-t." – M.: MGSU, 2012. – 200 p.
2. Adamenko O. A. Conceptual foundations of innovative development of enterprises. Scientific works of the National University of Food Technologies. 2010. No. 35. pp. 5-10.
3. Ilyashenko S.M. Innovative development management: problems, concepts, methods: textbook for students of higher education institutions. Sumy: VTD "University Book", 2003. 278 p.
4. Digital transformation of industrial management: theory and practice: monograph by mid. Doctor of Philosophy, Professor V.G.Voronkova, Doctor of Economics, Professor N.G.Metelenko. Lviv-Torun: Liha-Pres, 2023. 816 p.
5. Goryaschenko Yu. Management of innovative development of enterprises in the conditions of digitalization. Entrepreneurship and Innovation, 2021. (17), 34-38

